

Global Drought Impacts in Near-Real-Time: A Media-Based Database for Drought Impact Reporting

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Abstract. Drought impact monitoring is often limited by data availability in terms of both access to impact information and the effectiveness of data acquisition. These challenges have been partially addressed by employing the drought impact information accessed via text data (newspaper articles or online social network content). While this approach provides valuable insights, it remains constrained by temporal relevance, as data preparation is often retrospective and time-consuming. In this study, we introduce the Global Drought Impact Report Database, a system for the weekly collection and classification of drought impact data from online media sources, designed to support near-real-time monitoring. The database includes over 9400 drought impact reports from 152 countries. The database is updated weekly, and the results are publicly available at a pilot database content viewer. The database can serve as a complementary source for drought monitoring, early impact detection, and global impact analysis, and may support further assessment of drought monitoring systems.

Keywords: natural language processing, text mining, online media, drought impacts, large language models

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1. Introduction

Drought events, intensified by the ongoing climate change (Dai, 2013; Samaniego et al., 2018), have increasingly posed challenges to global food security (Trnka et al., 2019), water resource availability and quality (Delpla et al., 2009), and ecosystem stability and productivity (Ciais et al., 2005) and have had local to large-scale impacts on both ecosystems and society. According to recent estimates, the adverse effects of drought, compounded by factors such as food insecurity and lack of access to clean water, were associated with approximately 650,000 deaths worldwide from 1970–2019 period (World Meteorological Organization, 2021). Although statistics suggest that the impact of drought on lives has decreased in recent decades (World Meteorological Organization, 2021), the economic impacts of this phenomenon are growing and are expected to grow further. For example, the cost of drought in the United States in 2023 was estimated to be 14 billion dollars (Aon, 2024). In the European Union and the United Kingdom, the annual economic losses associated with droughts total 9 billion euros and this total is expected to rise to 65 billion euros annually (Naumann et al., 2021).

These developments and the challenging outlook have prompted efforts to map, track, analyze, and quantify the impacts of drought events. Although the critical importance of drought impact monitoring is now well understood (Lackstrom et al., 2013) and the drought research community has expanded its focus beyond drought indices and indicators (Stahl et al., 2016; Walker et al., 2024; National Drought Mitigation Center, 2024; Joint Research Centre, 2024), comprehensive and large-scale impact monitoring continues to face considerable technical and methodological challenges.

Multiple comprehensive drought impact assessment efforts have highlighted the importance of drought impact databases as valuable resources of information (Stahl et al., 2016; Jakubínský et al., 2019; de Brito et al., 2020; Trnka et al., 2020; Stephan et al., 2021; Meitner et al., 2023; O’Connor et al., 2022; National Drought Mitigation Center, 2024; Joint Research Centre, 2024). These examples of previous work demonstrate how various sources of information can be synthesized into comprehensive and structured collections of drought impacts. However, several challenges with this approach have been noted, such as the variable, cascading, and compound nature of drought impacts, as well as the significant effort required to collect and maintain this type of information in large-scale drought monitoring databases.

In this study, we present the newly developed Global Drought Impact Report Database (IDB), which is established via combined automated online content mining, text classification, and translation via large language models (LLMs), along with human-supervised weekly updates. Although both text mining and the application of language models have been verified as effective for collecting drought impact (de Brito et al., 2020; Lima Alencar et al., 2024; Sodoge et al., 2024), our approach addresses key challenges in the collection of global drought impact data, such as resource limitations, manual workload, and maintaining database continuity over time. Since 2022, 9464 drought impact reports (relevant to March 31, 2025, with the most up-to-date data available at <https://global-drought-impacts-browser.onrender.com/>) from online media have been compiled in the IDB, making it the first operational tool for global drought impact monitoring, offering near-real-time information with weekly updates.

2. Methods

The final IDB inputs are obtained via a combination of automated and human-supervised methods to achieve high data processing efficiency and high data quality and accuracy (Fig. 1). The methodological steps are repeated weekly to provide continuous data inputs. These steps include an automated multilingual search for relevant online media reports, automated full-text acquisition, automated full-text analysis and classification, automated translation of non-English drought impact information, supervised approval of IDB inputs and weekly database updates and data publication. A comprehensive technical overview, encompassing definitions, the extended methodology and the main methodological assumptions of IDB, is provided in the *Supplementary Material*.

Initial IDB data are collected via automated web searching algorithms in the Python programming language (version 3.10.0, released on May 10, 2021). Searching for relevant online media reports is based upon a predefined search query compiled from keywords and logical operators. For the IDB, a simple search query was designed in English, as follows:

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drought AND (impact OR agriculture
OR yield OR wildfire OR navigation
OR drinking water OR disease)
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The original English version of this query was further translated into 11 selected languages to cover global online media reports, including those

Figure 1. Weekly drought impact report processing workflow, including a) automated online media content mining with Python, b) full-text extraction of article content with Python scripts, c) automated text classification with the ChatGPT application programming interface, d) supervised database input approval by database editors and e) weekly database updates and data publication

in Arabic, Bengali, simplified Chinese, traditional Chinese, French, German, Hindi, Portuguese, Russian, Spanish, and Urdu. Translation and further processing of non-English results have been included since September 2023. The translated search queries are included in the Supplementary material (see Section 3, Figure 2).

A combination of two free-of-charge tools, namely the Python News application programming interface (API) (Lisiv, 2024) and Google API Python Client libraries (Fig. 1, a)) is used. Web searching is performed automatically every Monday at 8:00 a.m. UTC to search for articles matching the defined search query published in the last seven days (from the previous Monday to the previous Sunday). Both selected search methods support searching via a specific query based on which the relevant results are returned. All of the results (articles) are stored in an initial comma-separated file, which includes the article title, article uniform resource locator (URL), date of publication, name of publisher or source, and the original language of the article. Both selected methods have specific technical and usage limitations, described in the API documentation libraries (Lisiv, 2024; Google LLC) and considered in our methodological limitations and assumptions (Supplementary Material, Section 2, Table 1).

The next methodological step involves extracting the full text of each article from its URL (Fig. 1, b)) potentially with manual addition in later stages. This semiautomated process, implemented in Python, uses the Beautiful Soup (Richardson, 2007) and Requests (Chandra and Varanasi, 2015) libraries. Each URL is accessed, and the article's full text is extracted and appended to a comma-separated file. However, this automated extraction does not always succeed because of factors such as website protection against automated mining or the presence of unstructured content. In

such cases, the full text is manually added by the IDB editor.

Each full text is subsequently automatically preclassified and analysed via the OpenAI Python library, specifically with the GPT-4o language model (Open AI) (Fig. 1, c). The goal of this step is to automatically detect the category of the impact report and the time and location of the reported drought impacts to prepare structured information for direct import into IDB. For the systematic classification of impacts, 14 impact report categories were developed: (1) Soil, (2) Hydrology, (3) Agriculture, (4) Forestry, (5) Wildlife and plants, (6) Wildfires and fire occurrence, (7) Household water supply, (8) Health and society, (9) Energy production, (10) Industry, (11) Tourism, (12) Inland waterborne transportation, (13) Economy and technology and (14) Other. Each of the main categories is further structured into subcategories. The original set of impact categories was based on the structure of the European Drought Impact Inventory (EDII) (Stahl et al., 2016). However, since the IDB only includes online media reports, the categories were iteratively adjusted and refined based on impact narratives found in media reporting. Each impact category includes a definition and a list of key words available in the supplementary material (Supplementary material, Section 4, Table 5) as well as the original pairing of early-stage IDB content categories to EDII categories (Supplementary material, Section 4, Figure 3).

The precise geographical location of each impact report is recorded in IDB. The mandatory location information includes the continent and country of the impact event. Over 63 % of the impact reports are also assigned to lower geographical units, representing various levels of regional administration units for each country (GADM, 2024). For relevant impact reports, information on affected rivers or water bodies is also

included when mentioned in the original media articles. To extract this information, the processed full texts are used as inputs for the OpenAI Python library together with the so-called prompt – a set of instructions on how to process the full text input with the LLM. This workflow is used for both English results and results found in other languages. The final IDB inputs are stored in English. The prompt that is currently used (as of 10.05.2025) for impact report classification is as follows:

"Is following text about impacts of drought? If yes extract impacted country and region, information about time of event, and decide which of following impact types are valid: Soil, Hydrology, Agriculture, Forestry, Wildlife and plants, Wildfires and fire occurrence, Household water supply, Health and society, Energy production, Industry, Tourism, Inland waterborne transportation, Economy and technology, Other. Use only explicitly mentioned impact categories and do not suggest any other. Return the information in the following form: Impact categories: list of valid categories; Time: time of impact; Region: impact country and region"

The final step of the IDB methodology (Fig. 1, d)) consists of supervised preclassified data approval and the treatment of insufficient or incomplete IDB inputs. Weekly IDB inputs are checked and approved manually. Some of the automatically extracted information might be corrected or thoroughly checked and improved. Human supervision is involved for the majority of reports, to be approved and entered in the IDB. It includes supervision, corrections and assignments of geographical units, impact categories and subcategories, time references and additions of full-texts for the cases where it is not possible to extract these automatically. After the final data check, the weekly batch of new IDB inputs is uploaded to the database and processed into updated maps and charts of impact reports (Fig. 1, e)). All IDB inputs must represent the specific impact of drought events, defined as a negative direct or indirect consequence of drought in either society or ecosystems.

The IDB is organized as a structured relational database implemented in PostgreSQL to maintain geometries and coordinate systems for selected data elements. A set of required and optional parameters is stored for each impact report. The required parameters are a unique identifier, source article identifier, editor identifier, impact report category, impact report subcategory, impact report date, continent of impact

report and country of impact report. The optional parameters include the lower geographical unit of the impact report, a specific geography note, a river identifier, a water body identifier, and keywords and notes.

3. Results

3.1. Content of the Global drought impact report database

The IDB is updated weekly, covering the period from March 22, 2022, until the present, with its content continuously growing. The content description provided in this study reflects the content of IDB as of March 31, 2025. To date, IDB contains 9464 impact reports (Fig. 2, b)) reports from six continents, spanning 152 countries. Preliminary online access to the up-to-date database is available via a public prototype viewer at <https://global-drought-impacts-browser.onrender.com/>. The most represented countries include the United States of America (USA, 4507 impact reports), Spain (417 impact reports), the United Kingdom (UK, 327 impact reports), Kenya (281 impact reports) and Somalia (268 impact reports). The most frequent categories include Hydrology (2331 impact reports), Wildfires and fire occurrence (1828 impact reports), Agriculture (1667 impact reports) and Health and Society (1461 impact reports), with notable regional differences in the reported impact categories among continents (Fig. 2, c)). The least-common IDB impact categories are Other (6 impact reports), Forestry (26 impact reports) and Industry (26 impact reports). For most of the period, the search for new IDB inputs was limited to English-only results, highlighted by the high number of impact reports in North America and Europe. The number of impact reports collected has two peaks: one in the summer of 2022 and one in the autumn of 2023, underlining the severe drought events in Europe and South America, respectively, at those times.

3.2. Evaluating the global drought impact report database for effective drought and drought impact mapping

The summer and autumn of 2022 were marked by one of the most severe droughts Europe has experienced in recent decades. The persistent lack of precipitation and heat waves resulted in diverse drought impacts in agriculture, energy production, and river transportation (Toreti et al., 2022). During the June–September 2022 period, worsening soil drought and overall water deficiency conditions were showing large-scale severe drought events (Fig. 3). The timeline of selected drought indicators (soil moisture

Figure 2. Insights into the content of the global drought impact report database content, including a) the number of impact reports for each lower geographical unit available, b) the number of impact reports in the months of data collection and the cumulative number of impact reports and c) the share of impact report categories for each continent. Reflecting period from March 2022 to March 2025

deficit in 0-100 cm (SMD), a 4-week composite of evaporative stress index (ESI) and a 4-week composite of standardized precipitation evapotranspiration index (SPEI) highlights the extensive overall drought conditions in Western and Central Europe region (Fig. 3, b)) (as defined by IPCC reference region (Iturbide et al., 2020)).

The IDB includes 907 impact reports for the 2022 period (March 22–December 31), with the majority of impacts reported in the UK (301), Italy (146), and France (136). Each of the countries represents one of the regions with diverse drought conditions during 2022, with the highest impact reported in the UK.

The majority of UK impact reports focus on the public water supply, reflecting water use restrictions and shortages in UK households (Fig. 4, a)). The impact reports collected in France (Fig. 4, b)) indicate a much earlier onset of drought impacts, underlying the earlier onset of drought conditions in the region (Fig. 3, b)), with impacts reported mainly in the agricultural sector and higher wildfire occurrence and risk. The main impacted sector in Italy (Fig. 4, c))

was agriculture, with the onset of the drought impact following the early onset of the SMD and low SPEI values in the region (Fig. 3, c)).

4. Discussion

This study presents the first global drought impact monitoring system capable of providing near-real-time data while maintaining a lightweight operational workload. The system is designed for efficient data collection and processing and can be easily applied in operational services.

The importance of drought impact monitoring in comprehensive drought assessment has been recognized and addressed (Lackstrom et al., 2013; Walker et al., 2024), resulting in efforts to build and implement drought impact monitoring tools (Wilhite et al., 2007; Stahl et al., 2016; Trnka et al., 2020; Stephan et al., 2021; O'Connor et al., 2022). Our approach builds upon this experience by implementing automation and text data mining methods, which allows us to overcome some of the previously described technological and

Figure 3. Drought conditions in weeks (W00-W51) of the 2022 period as depicted by the share of the area with a soil moisture deficit in 0–100 cm (SMD) < 0, by the share of the area with a 4-week composite of evaporative stress index (ESI) < 0 and by share of the area with a 4-week composite of the standardized precipitation evapotranspiration index (SPEI) < -1 for a) Northern Europe (NEU) b) Central Europe (CEU) and c) the Mediterranean (MED) for each reference region highlighted in d)

Figure 4. Weekly share of reported impact categories in countries with the highest number of IDB reports, including a) the United Kingdom, b) France and c) Italy in 2022

methodological roadblocks (Stahl et al., 2016; de Brito et al., 2020; Sodoge et al., 2023). Compared to state-of-the-art regional drought impact databases like EDII (or its descendant, the European Drought Impact Database) and Drought Impact Reporter (DIR), the IDB approach brings global coverage independent of a structured reporting system or network. Although the IDB methodology does not support retrospective data collection (as one of the technical limitations is the low long term availability of online content (Hansen and Paul, 2015; Pew Research Center, 2024)) forand does not reach the same level of detail and confidence as traditional expert-based drought impact assessments, it offers a unique and timely resource that, to our knowledge, has not existed until now. This is a crucial addition to the current drought monitoring landscape, particularly for rapid post-event assessments, gap-filling in underrepresented regions, and operational support for agencies such as the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction.

These characteristics are essential for using the IDB in early warning systems, where it can serve as a resource for flagging emerging impact hotspots. This effect was also evident in our case study, which highlighted a high number of household water supply impact reports in the United Kingdom despite only moderate drought severity indicated by traditional indices (4, a)). The ability to detect such emerging hotspots may be even more valuable given the global and multilingual coverage of the IDB, particularly in supporting regions and languages that are underrepresented or difficult to reach through conventional monitoring networks and retrospective impact assessments (Huggel et al., 2015; Panwar and Sen, 2020; Fezzigna et al., 2025).

Recent studies have already shown how to employ text mining in natural hazard impact information analysis. Previous text mining efforts were often limited to a single drought event, resource type, or language, and impact assessments were often in retrospective nature (de Brito et al., 2020; Sodoge et al., 2023, 2024). Our approach provides new flexibility with the implementation of LLMs and automated text classification and supports the possibility of gathering data in near-real-time and in a sustained and continuous manner. Recent developments in LLMs and their quality and accessibility have aided in the development of IDB workflows, overcoming the significant issues of impact category assignment, and determining the spatiotemporal location of drought impacts identified in previous research (Stahl et al., 2016). This advancement also provides a basis for directly connecting impact information to indicator information at large scales, as these connections were highlighted as crucial in previous research (Bachmair et al., 2015).

The inclusion of multilingual processing in our workflow facilitates the reporting of global drought events and helps reduce the language bias common in traditional drought impact databases. This bias was also evident in the example of the 2022 drought event in Europe. The case study revealed a high number of impacts collected in the UK (Fig. 4, a)) despite the lower severity of drought events showed by indicators (Fig. 3, a)). A similar skew toward English-speaking and well-covered countries is visible across the entire IDB (Fig. 2, a)). Implementing multilingual processing (from September 2023 onward) yielded promising results for several widely used languages, particularly those with a strong online presence. However, comparable coverage has not yet been achieved for low-resource languages such as Urdu and Bengali (see Supplementary Material, Section 3, Table 2). This highlights a major pathway for future development of the IDB—namely, the refinement of translated search queries and the integration of region-specific news sources in collaboration with native speakers. In parallel, future integration of the IDB into an operational monitoring platform should be accompanied by transparent communication of dataset limitations. In particular, the density of reported impacts must not be interpreted as a direct proxy for drought severity, but rather as a complementary layer of information with added contextual value beyond traditional drought indices. Calculation of regional anomaly metrics, such as the media drought index, is necessary to understand local drought impact severity.

With sectoral-based impact categorization, as implemented in IDB, uncertainties in the connection of impacts and indicators, as noted in previous research (O'Connor et al., 2022), are also being reduced. Finally, the near-real-time nature of the IDB workflow can support the drought risk management efforts (Senay et al., 2015), which are dependent on drought monitoring and impact modeling, especially for areas where the impact information is often lacking (Kchouk et al., 2022). Future developments in this direction should also focus on spatio-temporal grouping of the IDB records to match better the real extent of drought events, including the lag of drought impact occurrence after the drought event (Slette et al., 2019; Shyrokaya et al., 2024), and lowering well-reported events bias, present in the IDB. As this manuscript focused on the methodology introduction, future validation and further development of the IDB workflow will focus on the temporal correlation of the IDB dataset and weekly and monthly drought indices, as well as regional validation of the IDB with state-of-the-art regional databases, such as the EDII and DIR.

Overall, IDB represents a significant step forward in leveraging online media as a timely and accessible

source of environmental information. Although technical and methodological challenges remain, our proof of concept demonstrates that advancements in LLMs and text processing have made the integration of online media into impact monitoring increasingly efficient and effective.

5. Conclusion

In this study, the Global Drought Impact Report Database is presented as an innovative pilot solution to drought impact monitoring and assessment challenges, particularly in terms of data availability and timeliness. By leveraging automated data collection from online media reports, the database effectively reduces the time gap between the occurrence of drought impacts and their reporting. The IDB remains under active development, and it would benefit from collaboration with other research teams and regional experts to further enhance its accuracy, language coverage, and representativeness, particularly for low-resource regions. The weekly updates and public accessibility through the pilot website at <https://global-drought-impacts-browser.onrender.com/> and future integration with the terradrought.edu platform (currently under development) provide excellent utility, offering valuable support for both research and practical applications in drought and drought impact management.

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Appendix A. Appendix I: List of abbreviations

API - Application programming interface
CEU - Western and Central Europe region
DIR - Drought impact reporter
EDII - European drought impact inventory
ESI - Evaporative stress index
IDB - Global Drought Impact Report Database
LLM - Large language model
MED - Mediterranean region
NEU - Northern Europe region
SMD - Soil moisture deficit
SPEI - Standardized precipitation evapotranspiration index
URL - Uniform resource locator